

OpenMod Africa

OM4A ToolBox

DELIVERABLE NO. 4.2

Funded by
the European Union

This report is licensed under a Creative Commons Licence

Attribution 4.0 International License

Deliverable No.	D4.2	Work Package No.	WP4
Work Package Title	Open Modelling for Africa (OM4A) Toolbox		
Dissemination level	PU		
Due date	2025-06-30		
Version	V1.1		
Status	Final		
Submission date	2025-10-21		

Deliverable Contributors	Name	Organisation	Date
Deliverable Leader	Philip Hackstock	IIASA	2025-06-15
Work Package Leader	Sandrine Charousset	EDF	2025-06-15
Contributing Author(s)	Sandrine Charousset	EDF	2025-06-15
	Jonathan Hanto	TU Berlin	2025-06-15
	Jeremy Dumoulin	EPFL	2025-06-15
	Jean-Marie Alder	HES-SO	2025-06-15
	David Wannier	HES-SO	2025-06-15
	Gwenaelle Gustin	HES-SO	2025-06-15
	David Gianadda	HES-SO	2025-06-15
	Alain Duc	HES-SO	2025-06-15
	Philip Hackstock	IIASA	2025-06-15
Reviewer(s)	Andres Ramos	Comillas	2025-06-25
	Giulia Vaglietti	FEEM	2025-06-25
Final review and approval	Ingeborg Graabak	SINTEF	2025-06-30

History of Change

Release	Date	Reason for Change	Status
V0	2025-05-30	First draft	Draft
V1	2025-06-30	First release	Final
V1.1	2025-10-21	EU emblem and funding text updated.	Final

DISCLAIMER / ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101118123.

This report is licensed under a Creative Commons Licence

Attribution 4.0 International License

For more information about the Creative Commons Licence, including the full legal text, please visit: <https://creativecommons.org/use-remix/cc-licenses/>

Table of contents

1	Introduction.....	7
2	The OM4A ToolBox.....	8
2.1	Models.....	8
2.1.1	GENeSYS-MOD.....	9
2.1.2	openTEPES.....	9
2.1.3	plan4res.....	9
2.1.4	InfraFair.....	9
2.1.5	OnSSET.....	9
2.1.6	EV-PV.....	10
2.2	Data.....	10
2.2.1	The database: the Scenario Explorer.....	10
2.2.2	The IAMC nomenclature.....	10
2.2.3	The pyam package.....	11
2.3	Case Studies.....	11
2.4	Training.....	11
2.5	Visualisation.....	11
2.6	Permanent Network.....	12

List of Abbreviations

CSV	Comma Separated Values
EAPP	Eastern African Power Pool
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIS	Geographic Information System
HV	High Voltage
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change
OM4A	Open Modelling ToolBox For Africa
OPEX	OPerating EXpenditure
POI	Point Of Interest
PTDF	Power Transfer Distribution Factor
PV	PhotoVoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy System
SSV	Seasonal Storage Valuation
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UC	Unit Commitment
WAPP	Western African Power Pool

List of Figures

Figure 1: OM4A ToolBox main menu.....	8
---------------------------------------	---

Executive Summary

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling ToolBox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about the development of an energy modelling ToolBox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building in the use of models and further development of the ToolBox, among African experts, is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling ToolBox. The OM4A ToolBox is populated with a suite of open, integrated, state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting, among others, scenario building exercises at regional, national and pan-African level. Two case studies are being conducted to demonstrate the use of the ToolBox, and in addition provide new insights into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with two stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool region and one in the Western African Power Pool region.

This deliverable consists of the release of the OM4A ToolBox, which is now (publicly) available at the following links:

OM4A ToolBox	africaenergymodels.net	
Permanent network	africanenergymodellingnetwork.net	
Training material	github OM4A-Training-Material	
Models		
Model name	Main github	OM4A training material
GENeSYS-MOD	https://github.com/GENeSYS-MOD	GENeSYS-MOD training material
openTEPES	https://github.com/IIT-EnergySystemModels/opentepes	openTEPES training material
plan4res	https://github.com/plan4res	Plan4res training material
EV-PV	https://github.com/evpv-simulator	EV-PV training material
InfraFair	https://github.com/IIT-EnergySystemModels/InfraFair	InfraFair training material
OnSSET	https://github.com/OnSSET	OnSSET training material

This document is the accompanying report to the deliverable. It consists in a description of the ToolBox and how to use it.

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling ToolBox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about development of an energy modelling ToolBox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building among African experts in use and development of the ToolBox is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling ToolBox. The ToolBox will be populated with a suite of open integrated state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting among other scenario building exercises at regional, national and pan-African level. Two case studies are demonstrating the use of the ToolBox, and in addition providing new insight into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with two stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool region and one in the Western African Power Pool region.

The objectives of WP4, Open Modelling for Africa ToolBox (OM4A) are the following:

1. Based on The Open Platform from the H2020 project openENTRANCE, develop the OM4A ToolBox as collection of integrated and fully open state-of-the-art tools and a database for storing and exchanging data.
2. Develop a catalogue of models mapped with modelling needs.
3. Develop tools for presentation of assumptions and results of pathways for development of secure, sustainable and cost-efficient energy systems in regions in Africa.
4. Develop materials for training African scientific experts in using the ToolBox for exploring pathways for energy systems.
5. Train one African scientific partner in maintaining the database.

This deliverable aims at completing Objective 1, i.e., the development of the OM4A ToolBox, which is now (publicly) available at the following link: <https://africaenergymodels.net/>

This document is the accompanying report to the deliverable. It consists in a description and use manual of the ToolBox itself.

2 The OM4A ToolBox

This chapter introduces and explains the OM4A open energy system modelling ToolBox, which can be accessed via <https://africaenergymodels.net/>. The open energy modelling ToolBox contains the models (see list and summary in section 2.1) but it also provides all the necessary supporting materials such as the installation- & use guides, general description and preliminary results of the case studies conducted in OM4A to test the modelling ToolBox, a database (the Scenario Explorer), and a tool to visualize the results from the case studies. The Scenario explorer at a later stage will be populated with datasets related to the openMod4Africa case studies.

The long-term maintenance of the ToolBox, beyond the OM4A Project, will be granted by the Permanent Network, a community of African energy modelling experts and stakeholders (see <https://africanenergymodellingnetwork.net/>). For this reason, the ToolBox website also refers to the Permanent Network website, and to its support forum. Overall, [africaenergymodels](https://africaenergymodels.net/) is a comprehensive platform dedicated to advancing energy system modelling across the African continent. It is specifically designed to support policymakers, researchers, and practitioners in developing robust, data-driven energy strategies that are aligned with Africa's unique development priorities and sustainability goals.

This website facilitates the use of energy models that reflect the continent's diverse geographic, economic, and social contexts. By offering access to open-source tools, high-quality datasets, and opportunities for collaboration, [africaenergymodels](https://africaenergymodels.net/) empowers its users to analyse and plan effective, sustainable energy transitions. The energy system modelling efforts conducted through the platform consider critical factors such as rapid population growth, expanding economic activities, infrastructure development, and the urgent need to address climate change.

In doing so, the platform serves, not only as a technical resource hub, but also as a catalyst for building local capacity and fostering regional cooperation in the energy modelling community across Africa.

Its general structure is explained below:

Figure 1: OM4A ToolBox main menu

The main page when accessing [africaenergymodels](https://africaenergymodels.net/) enables the users to navigate between multiple subpages (see Figure 1 that will be explained in the following subsections).

2.1 Models

On the Models subpage, users are presented with an overview of all the models available in the OM4A Open Energy System Modelling ToolBox. Through provided links, users can access individual pages for each model, which offer more detailed information as well as links to the respective GitHub repositories where the models can be accessed to be installed and used.

The following models are included:

2.1.1 GENeSYS-MOD

The Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is a linear open-source energy system model which is tailored to analyze long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transport. First published by Löffler et al. (2017), it extends the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSEMOSYS) framework and, since then, it has been expanded to include numerous additional features and functionalities. Its main strength lies in its ability to simultaneously optimize the capacity expansion, energy generation, and dispatch of the system for all the main energy sectors, which leads to an endogenous optimization of the entire energy system. This then also takes into account the additional electricity demand from sector coupling by considering interactions between all energy sectors, as well as storage, grid, and other flexibility requirements.

2.1.2 openTEPES

The openTEPES model is a decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and (electricity, hydrogen, and heat) network dynamic expansion plan of a large-scale electric system at a tactical level¹. The user pre-defines the expansion candidates, so that the model determines the optimal decisions among those specified by the user as possible. Essentially, any power related technology focused on generation and storage can be considered by this tool, including the conventional generation units (thermal -nuclear, gas, coal), energy storage of different types (hydro, pumped-hydro, battery, electric vehicle, demand response, electrolyzer, solar thermal) and variable renewable (onshore and offshore wind power, solar PV, run-of-the-river). Besides, the representation of the hydro system based on volume and water inflow data considers the water stream topology (hydro cascade basins).

2.1.3 plan4res

plan4res is a power system model, which includes capacity expansion (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections of a given year), optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and simulation of the system operation. plan4res focuses on electricity. It includes all power generation technologies, electricity storage technologies, and a (usually aggregated) representation of the interconnections between regions (the transmission grid within one region is not represented, nevertheless, the granularity of regions can be adapted to the modelling needs).

2.1.4 InfraFair

The InfraFair model determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries. Based on this utilisation and if it reflects the economic benefits received by agents, it determines the responsibility of each agent in the construction of each element in the network. To reasonably reflect the stakeholder's utilisation of network infrastructure, multiple representative snapshots of the annual network usage should be provided. InfraFair is a decision support tool for network cost allocation and tariff design for regional power transmission infrastructure, but it can be used for national infrastructure as well as other types of infrastructures operating on the same principle of flow (e.g. gas and hydrogen). Hence, the model considers all assets that have a flow usage such as power lines, transformers, breaks, series capacitors and phase shifting transformers.

2.1.5 OnSSET

The Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) is a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas. In particular, OnSSET is a bottom-up medium- to long-term optimization model that

¹ Tactical planning is concerned with time horizons of 10-20 years

attempts to determine the least-expensive supply option to achieve universal electrification in each site by combining population settlements with various geographical features, socioeconomic data, and demographic information. The OnSSET code base is modular and allows the users to specify spatial and temporal resolution of the analysis, GIS input data, technologies and costs.

2.1.6 EV-PV

EV-PV is a model designed to support decision-making and strategic planning for electric mobility within a specific region. Originally developed as a set of geospatial data layers and calculation modules within the Citiwatts platform (<https://citiwatts.eu/>), it has been transformed, within the scope of this project, into a standalone tool with expanded features to address the unique challenges of Africa's transport landscape. The EV-PV model now comes as an integrated framework for analyzing private passenger mobility demand, electric vehicle (EV) charging needs, the potential of photovoltaic (PV) energy to meet these needs, and the required charging infrastructure. The model can be run entirely using openly available geospatial datasets, making it a solution for data-scarce environments. For PV generation, it supports a range of installation archetypes, such as rooftop and free-standing systems, enabling flexible assessments.

2.2 Data

The Data page contains a link to the openMod4Africa database, <https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/openmod4africa>, (currently empty), which will later in the project contain the main (public) datasets of the project, as well as information about the (IAMC) data format used in the project, the nomenclature of variables and a ToolBox for processing data using the IAMC format.

2.2.1 The database: the Scenario Explorer

During the project, we use two Scenario Explorers, an access-restricted instance for project-internal data exchange and a public one for publication. The project internal Scenario Explorer can be found here: <https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/openmod4africa-internal> and the public one (which will be made available once the case studies will have populated it with results) under this address: <https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/openmod4africa>. The Scenario Explorer is an online tool for sharing, comparing and analysing scenario data.

2.2.2 The IAMC nomenclature

This section provides users with detailed information on the standardized variable template and nomenclature package used across the OM4A ToolBox. These resources define a consistent structure for variables, regions, and units used in energy system models, supporting transparency, interoperability, and collaboration across modelling teams.

On this page, users can find:

- An explanation of the variable template: A shared list of variables with hierarchical naming conventions that follow international standards, designed for clarity and compatibility across models. [openentrance/definitions at main · openENTRANCE/openentrance](#)
- Region definitions: A structured classification of geographic areas, from global and regional aggregates to individual countries and sub-national regions (e.g., NUTS levels and e-highway2050 clusters).
- Details on directional data: Guidelines for representing flows between regions (e.g., Norway>Germany).

As well as the link to the GitHub repository where this nomenclature is maintained.

2.2.3 The pyam package

The pyam (<https://pyam-iamc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>) package is an open-source python library that enables users to work with IAMC-style data (<https://pyam-iamc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/data.html>), generate plots, perform analysis and download data directly from IIASA Scenario Explorers. It is mainly developed by IIASA with contributions from the integrated assessment community.

2.3 Case Studies

The Case Studies page provides an overview of how the OM4A ToolBox is being used in real-world applications across Africa, featuring summaries that demonstrate its capacity to support energy planning and policy development. It serves as a practical reference for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners interested in how the ToolBox is applied to address Africa's energy challenges.

On this page (<https://africaenergymodels.net/case-studies/>), users find detailed descriptions of the regional case studies in West Africa and East Africa—including the objectives, leading institutions, geographic focus, and key themes considered. This page outlines the scope of each study, such as mini-grids, electrification, and national and regional energy system analyses. It also highlights how the ToolBox supports both technical insights and capacity building in local contexts.

2.4 Training

The **Training** section provides links for users to access training materials for all the models available in the OM4A ToolBox, hosted under <https://github.com/OM4A-Training-Material>. This GitHub organization contains individual repositories for each model, offering a wide range of resources to support users in effectively working with the models. Furthermore, YouTube videos are provided to further enable the users to explore the main functionalities of the model (Installation, how to run the model etc.). The YouTube videos are hosted in a dedicated youtube channel, [Africanenergymodellingnetwork](https://www.youtube.com/@africanenergymodellingnetwork) (<https://www.youtube.com/@africanenergymodellingnetwork>), which is maintained by the project's Permanent Network.

2.5 Visualisation

The **Visualisation** section (<https://africaenergymodels.net/visualisation/>) offers an interactive way to explore the scenarios and case studies from the OM4A ToolBox. At the centre of the page is a map-based tool that allows users to visually engage with the geographic and model-based data.

Users can browse available case studies and scenarios directly on the map, gaining insights into how the OM4A models can be applied to different regions across the continent. For a more detailed and immersive experience, the page includes a button linking to the full version of the visualisation tool on its dedicated platform. This enables deeper exploration of data, model outputs, and regional energy system dynamics in an intuitive and user-friendly format.

When entering the section, users can click the provided link, which opens a dedicated platform for an immersive experience in exploring data, model outputs, and energy system dynamics across multiple spatial scales.

Relevant visualisations have been integrated for all models within the ToolBox (e.g., pie charts for InfraFair cost allocation, graphs showing flows for models like openTepes and Plan4Res, and more). Some open-source geospatial data layers are also included to complement the model outputs.

Users can also create an account to upload their own datasets, which can be kept private or shared with other users. In future developments, the platform will incorporate so-called "calculation modules," similar to those used in the Citiwatts platform. These modules will perform data processing and could serve as user interfaces for GIS-based models such as EV-PV.

2.6 Permanent Network

This menu item is a link to the webpage of the African Energy Modelling Network (<https://africanenergymodellingnetwork.net/>), which highlights its core activities, including training, research support, and capacity building, and emphasizes its role in fostering innovation and providing evidence-based insights for policy and planning. It also presents the network's broader goal of enabling a just and sustainable energy transition by connecting academia, industry, and policymakers. The network hosts a Forum to allow interactions and support also concerning the use and results from the OM4A ToolBox.